

THE IMPACT OF DIGITALISATION ON INDIAN BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract:

"Digitalisation" has become the new trend in every industry. The banking sector is moving toward digitization in India. Banks are offering digital facilities to their customers. Digitalization adoption is a major change in the banking industry. Banking industries have improved their customer service by adopting digitization. Manual procedures and activities have all been changed into digital services in the digitalization of the banking era. Due to online banking, customers now have access to banks 24 hours in a day. Customers no longer need to keep cash on hand and they can make a payment anytime using an online payment system at any location. Digitalization of banking has resulted in cost savings tools for the banking industries and it resulted in to increase in revenue.

Digitalization of banking is customer-friendly therefore it takes place of traditional banking. India is moving towards a cashless economy. Digitalization of banking plays an important role to move India towards a cashless economy. At the same time, the digital revolution faced digital challenges therefore financial stability, as well as consumer protection, is an important aspect for the banking sector while the digitalizing banking sector.

Keywords: *Digitalisation, Banking Sector, traditional banking, online banking.*

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Introduction:

The process of turning data into a digital representation is known as digitization. The adoption of technology is referred to as digitalization. Due to online banking, customers now have access to banks 24 hours a day. Customers need not manage cash. Customers

can easily pay online using digital banking facilities so that the digitalization of banking is profitable to customers as well as the banking sector. ATM Machine, RTGS, NEFT, IMPS, Mobile Banking, Internet Banking are various tools of digital banking transactions. Digital Banking is a flexible and strong digital platform that allows users to increase their agility and speed. The focus of this article is on the impact of digitalization on banking.

Research Methodology:

1. Primary Data: This study relies on primary data. It contains interviews of Banking employees
2. Secondary Data: Secondary data includes things like the internet, banking websites etc.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the digitalisation of banking sector
2. To study various tools used in digitalisation of banking
3. To study impact of digitalisation on banking sector

Hypothesis:

1. H1 - Digitalisation of Banking has increased banking transactions.
2. H1 – Indian Banking industry moving towards a digital economy.

Digital Payment Methods:

1. Banking cards

Banking cards are one of the most extensively used payment methods, offering a variety of features and benefits such as payment security. These cards offer two-factor authentication for safe payments, such as a secure PIN and a one-time password (OTP). Card payment systems include RuPay, Visa, and MasterCard, to name a few. Banking cards can be used for online shopping, digital payment apps, point-of-sale machines, and internet transactions. They save both customers and businesses time and money, making transactions more convenient.

2. USSD

Another sort of digital payment technique is *99#, which may be used to make mobile payments without having to download an app. The USSD and the National Payments Corporation of India are both supporting this service (NPCI). The *99# service was developed to bring banking services to the masses across the country. Customers can use this service by dialling *99# on their mobile phone, which is a "Common number across all Telecom Service Providers (TSPs)" and transacting through an interactive

menu displayed on the mobile screen. Interbank account to account financial transfers, balance inquiries, and mini statements are just a few of the services available through the *99# service.

3. AEPS

AEPS can be utilised for balance inquiries, cash withdrawals, cash deposits, and aadhaar to aadhaar fund transfers, among other financial transactions. All of these transactions are completed through a banking correspondent who verifies Aadhaar data. If an individual's aadhaar is registered with a bank where he or she has a bank account, this service is available.

4. UPI

UPI is a new digital payment system that allows anyone with a bank account to send money to anyone else's bank account via a UPI-based app. UPI-enabled payments are made at all hours of the day, every day of the year. The service allows a user to link multiple bank accounts to a UPI app on their smartphone, allowing them to seamlessly conduct financial transfers and collect requests 24 hours a day. E.g. Google pay, Paytm etc

5. Mobile Wallets

Another common payment method is mobile wallets. Users can load money into their virtual wallets using debit or credit cards, and then utilise that money to conduct digital transactions. PayTM, Mobikwik, PhonePe, and others are some of the most popular mobile wallets.

6. Internet Banking

Internet banking is the process of conducting financial transactions over the internet. Many services, such as transferring funds, making a new fixed or recurring deposit, cancelling an account, and so on, are available. E-banking or virtual banking are other terms for internet banking. Internet banking is typically used to make NEFT, RTGS, or IMPS online fund transfers.

7. Mobile Banking

Mobile banking refers to the method of doing financial or banking operations via a smartphone. With the development of several mobile wallets, digital payment apps, and other services like the UPI, the scope of mobile banking is only growing. Many banks have their own apps which consumers can use to conduct banking operations at the touch of a button.

8. Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM) app

The BHIM app lets users to use the UPI application to make payments. This also works with UPI, and transactions can be completed with the help of a VPA. Money can be transferred to various bank accounts, virtual addresses, or Aadhaar numbers. Many banks have also partnered with the NPCI and BHIM to provide customers with access to this interface.

Trends of Digitalisation of Banking Sector in India.

Chart No 1

Payment systems experienced a robust growth in volume of 44.2 percent in 2019-20 and 26.2% growth in volume during 2020-21. Chart No 1

Chart No 2

In terms of value, the contractionary trend that began the 2019-20 (-1.2%) accelerated and saw a reduction of 13.4%, and a decrease in paper-based instrument transactions. The

lack of economic activity due to covid19 pandemic is largely to blame for the drop in the value of RTGS transactions. During 2020-21, the share of digital transactions in total non-cash retail payments climbed to 98.5 %, up from 97% the 2019-20. Chart No 2

During the initial stages of the nationwide lockdown due to the COVID-19 epidemic, payments decreased. However, as the lockdown was gradually relaxed, the value and volume of payments increased. Chart No 1

Among the electronic modes of payment, the number of transactions using RTGS increased by 5.7 percent during 2020-21, with a total value of 1,056 lakh crore, a decrease of 19.5 percent from the 2019-20, owing to a reduction in large value corporate transactions in line with the slowdown in economic activity. During the 2020-21, transactions through the National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) system increased by 12.7%.

Chart No 3

Chart No 3 shows trend of the digital payment volume and value. Due to covid19 pandemic during the year 2019-20 chart shows decreasing trend but in the year 2020-21 it shows increasing trend. In terms of volume digital transaction are increased even in covid19 pandemic.

After covid19 pandemic economic activities are increased. Authorization of Payment System Operators of Mobile Banking Providers for the year 2019-20 were 540, it increases to 566 in the year 2020-21.it will boost digitalisation of banking sector.

Chart No. 3

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, mobile app-based payments decreased. However, as the lockdown was relaxed, mobile app-based the value of payments increased. After the Covid19 pandemic, mobile app-based transaction value increased.

Conclusion:

The Indian Banking sector is moving towards a digital economy. Banking cards, USSD, AEPS, UPI Mobile Wallets, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, BHIM app are a user-friendly digital payment method that allows customers to transfer or receive money easily. Using these methods customers can check their balance, make a payment or many more banking transactions can be done therefore Indian retail customers moving towards a digital cashless economy. In the Covid19 pandemic (2019-20) large payment transactions are reduced due to the shutdown of the economy but digital transactions are increasing in terms of volume. growth in the volume of 44.2 percent in 2019-20 and 26.2% growth in volume during 2020-21.

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